

Detecting Distributed Reflection Dos Attack Using Kendall's Tau Rank Correlation

Durga M.¹,

¹SRM University, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India. E-mail: durga.it2@gmail.com

Abstract – DDoS attack is a major threat to internet, it makes a system or a network resources unavailable to legitimate users. A Distributed Reflected Denial of Service (DRDoS) involves sending forged requests of some type to a very large number of computers that will reply to the requests. Most of the mechanism for DRDoS detection related with specific protocols, but the rank correlation based detection is protocol independent. The attacker send the attack flow to reflectors, the reflectors send the responsive flow to the victim. So the converged responsive flow packet rate may have linear relationship with one another. Based on this observation, the kendall's tau rank correlation method is used to differentiate reflection flow from legitimate flow and discard malicious flows

Keywords: Security, DoS, DRDoS, Kendall's Tau Rank Correlation, Spearman Correlation

I. Introduction

Denial of Service (DoS) is a serious threat to the availability of services in computer networks and infrastructures. To guard against DoS attacks, a number of countermeasures have been designed and implemented based on traffic features tried to use three dimensions, traffic patterns, and client characteristics and file reference characteristics, to discriminate the flash event from DoS attacks. In a Distributed DoS (DDoS) attack, an attacker compromises a number of other network plugged machines and forms a DoS attack network to send the attack traffic simultaneously to the victim from various machines.

An effective technique that allows for amplification of the attack from a single source is a Distributed Reflected DoS (DRDoS) attack. The DRDoS attacks are based on request-response relationships existing in various situations. The attacker would simply craft packets with the return address of the intended victim, and send those packets to the broadcast address of the reflector network. These packets would effectively reach all available and responsive hosts on that particular network and elicit a response from them. Since the return address of the requests was forged by the victim address, the response would be sent to the victim in the form of large volume network flow. Those response packets become real attack packets against the victim. Although an attacker can send any type of packet as a request, types of response packets are limited by protocol specification and are predictable. The attacker needs to know only the IP address of a host to use it as a reflector.

Therefore, all the hosts in the Internet can potentially be used as reflectors. The attacker can increase attack sources easily and safely, unlike DDoS attacks which need slaves. This means it is possible to attack the victim

with low traffic from each attack sources. Besides, the attacker can also shift easily the attack source.

Detecting DRDoS attacks at a reflector needs sharing of information among potential reflectors about illegal traffic [9]. But the attacker can limit the number of request packet sending to each reflector, it makes difficult to detect attack at the reflector [7]. The DRDoS attacker exploit the connectionless request-response based protocols, so the isolation of attack traffic near the reflector is also difficult. But it is still necessary to detect DRDoS at places beside the victim. Ingress filtering has not been largely deployed, even though it is a hopeful solution [2]. DRDoD attacker can use lot of protocols to launch attack, the detection mechanisms are based on the type of protocol used. So the countermeasure requires all possible protocols and need to be update periodically. There is a need for the detection mechanism to be a protocol-independent method to detect most of attacks.

This paper concentrates the protocol-independent method of detecting DRDoS attack near victim. Rank Correlation method is used to discriminate DRDoS attack traffic from normal traffic. Kendall's Tau Rank correlation is a statistical method to find correlation between flows. Once the victim alerts upstream router about attack, then the router will sample the number of packets and test rank correlation between flows. The correlation value is used to decide the DRDoS attack.

II. Related Work

In [5], the DRDoS attack detection is based on the packet marking technique. The packet marking technique is a dynamic method here. The victim will detect the attack and trace back the attack using the IP address. The dynamic packet marking technique is implemented in the edge routers. The edge router can filter, store/retrieve and mark the incoming packet [11]. It must filter (drop)

incoming broadcast packet. After receiving every inbound packet, the router stores some parts of the packet header information which are packet source address, packet destination address, packet identification filed and header flags. Before adding this information to the list, the router checks to see if it is a new record or just stored before. The duplication is not allowed in the list and the previous record is overwritten. Based on this information dynamic marking can be done. The source attacker can be traced back. Due to the dynamic marking, the system becomes complex in the high traffic times. Detection and trace back needs extra packets to identify attacker

In [3], the detection method uses only pair of request/response, and does not need complicated state management. The detector beside the victim monitors both request and response packets because request/response is a bi-directional action. When the response packet is arrived, the detector will check the corresponding request. If it is confirmation of the response packet is failed, it will discard the response packet. Because the limited and predictable types of packets are used for attack as previously mentioned, it is possible to accurately detect reflected response by checking only limited type of pair between request and response. This detection system depends on the certainty of pair of request and response. The major disadvantage of this detection system is protocol dependent

. In [8], the DDoS attack detection is based on the correlation coefficient. The correlation coefficient is among the suspicious flows. This flow similarity-based approach is to discriminate DDoS attacks from flash crowds. They cluster the network packets that share the same destination address as one network flow, when the victim alerts the router about attack. The router samples the suspicious flow per unit time. The pearson's correlation coefficient can be applied to the sampled data. using the coefficient values they predict attack or legitimate flow [10]. The attack flows are discarded in the router itself. The legitimate flow is forwarded to the victim. The Pearson correlation coefficient is very sensitive. Due to the background legitimate flow, the efficiency of detection is reduced

In [6], the proposed DDoS detection method is based on some property of attack flow. Here they have taken the packages distribution behaviors. Sample the suspicious flow for number of packages and calculate the distance. The distance and threshold is compared to distinguish the attack and legitimate flow. The attack flows are discarded in the router itself. The legitimate flow is forwarded to the victim. The detection method depends on the property of the flows i.e network traffic. The attacker can trick the detection system to believe the attack flow as legitimate flow.

Hence the protocol independent method of detecting DRDoS attack is needed. Kendall's tau(τ) correlation coefficient, is a statistic used to measure the association between two measured quantities. The association

between the suspicious flows can be obtained using kendall's tau coefficient. So that the detection becomes simple and the system may perform well.

III. Analysis of Proposed System

The system design involves multiple reflectors, one attacker and one victim. The attacker sends the spoofed request to the entire reflector. On receiving the spoofed request, the entire reflector sends response to the victim. we formulate all packets to the victim through one router as a flow. The suspicious flows are sampled per unit time T for the packet count. Set the start time as t, so that the time interval is $[t, t+T]$. Normally one request packet generates one reply packet. The attack packet received by the victim should be generated by reflectors, it should be sent little earlier by the attacker. So the number of the reflector used by the attacker can be determined by the number of packets received in the victim. For a particular time interval, the number of packets in flows f1 and f2 are propositional. So the count of received packets per time unit for f1 to f2 represent a linear relationship, it can be expressed by correlation coefficient. It can be possible to detect attack when two or more attacker attack at the same time but all have to share the same set of reflectors. The detection is based on the fact that the generated packets in reflectors are the immediate result of arrived packets from the attacker. So in the routers, packets having the same destination are classified as single flow. When the victim alerts the upstream router about the ongoing attack, the router will sample the packets. The packet count of suspicious flows is sampled per time unit in the router. Tau value can be obtained from Kendall's tau rank correlation coefficient when it is applied to the sampled data. If the tau value lies between lower and upper threshold, then the flows are legitimate flow and forwarded to the destination. If not, it is considered as attack flow and discarded in the router itself. These thresholds are obtained by different attacking test cases

IV. Algorithm

Kendall tau is a non-parametric correlation coefficient that can be used to assess and test correlations between non-intervals scaled ordinal variables. Frequently the Greek letter τ (tau), is use to abbreviate the Kendall tau correlation coefficient. The Kendall tau correlation coefficient is considered to be equivalent to the Spearman rank correlation coefficient. While Spearman rank correlation coefficient is like the Pearson correlation coefficient but computed from ranks, the Kendall tau correlation rather represents a probability.

Kendall's Tau rank correlation coefficient is a measure of the association between two scalar or ordinal variables. Let $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ be a set of observations. The pair is said to be concordant pair, if

both $x_i > x_j$ and $y_i > y_j$ or if both $x_i < x_j$ and $y_i < y_j$. The pair is said to be concordant pair discordant pair if $x_i > x_j$ and $y_i < y_j$ or if $x_i < x_j$ and $y_i > y_j$. The Kendall's tau can be calculated by $\tau = (C-D)/N$, where $N = (n(n-1))/2$

Where C be the number of concordant pair, D be the number of discordant pair and n be the number of sample. The value range of $r_{X,Y}$ is $[-1,1]$, closer to 1 represents stronger positive linear relationship while closer to -1 represents stronger negative linear relationship, whereas 0 means no linear relationship

Normally in Rank Correlation based Detection, for two pure attacking flows namely f_a and f_b have the correlation coefficient will be close to 1. In the case of internet, it will vary due to the legitimate traffic. But the correlation coefficient between two attack flows should be strong when compared with other flows. Two threshold δ_1 and δ_2 are used to judge whether the flows are legitimate or attack. If $R_{a,b}$ value lies between upper and lower threshold means the two flows are legitimate flows. If not, it will be considered as attack flow. The steps involved in the algorithms is that

- Locate suspicious flows on an upstream router.
- Sample the number of packets of suspicious flows per time unit T for a short time, get the value sequence for each flow
- Submit sequences to a detection center, which will divide flows into pairs and calculate coefficient for each pair
- Compare coefficients for suspicious flows and make decision using threshold.
- If confirmed, then discard these flows on the routers

V. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper concentrates on detecting DRDoS independent of specific protocols, and proposed the Rank Correlation based Detection (RCD) algorithm. Once suspicious flows found, RCD starts to calculate the rank correlation between flow pairs and give final alert according to preset thresholds. The result could also be used to pick out and discard malicious flows. We can achieve low false negative and false positive. There are a lot of interesting works in the future, including

- Other correlation-like measurement and the comparison of their effectiveness,
- Extensive experiment against real DRDoS in the Internet,
- Using RCD in more sophisticated situation,
- What the attackers can do to escape detection and the countermeasures

References

- [1] C. Jin, H. Wang and K. Shin, "Hop-Count Filtering: An Effective Defense Against Spoofed Traffic", Proceedings of the 10th ACM

International Conference on Computer and Communications Security (CCS), pp. 30-41 (2003)

- [2] G. van Rooij, "Real Stateful TCP Packet Filtering in IP Filter", 10th USENIX Security Symposium (2001).
- [3] Hiroshi TSUNODA and Yoshiaki NEMOTO, "A Simple Response Packet Confirmation Method for DROS Detection" Feb ICAOT 2006 pp 1557-156.
- [4] P. Ferguson and D. Senie, "Network ingress filtering: defeating denial of service attacks which employ IP source address spoofing." Available: <http://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc2827.txt>.
- [5] Reza Shokrit, Ali Varshovi, Hossein Mohammadi, Nasser Yazdani, Babak Sadeghian "DDPM: Dynamic Deterministic Packet Marking for IP Traceback" Proceedings of IEEE 2006..
- [6] Shui Yu, Wanlei Zhou, Robin Doss, "Information Theory Based Detection Against Network Behavior Mimicking DDoS Attacks." IEEE COMMUNICATIONS LETTERS, VOL. 12, NO. 4, APRIL 2008, pp 319-121.
- [7] S. K. Rayanchu and G. Barua, "Defending against Slave and Reflector Attacks with Deterministic Edge Router Marking (DFRM)" Proceedings of the National Conference on Communications, NCC-2005 (2005)
- [8] S. Yu, W. Zhou, W. Jia, S. Guo, Y. Xiang, and F. Tang, "Discriminating DDoS attacks from flash crowds using flow correlation coefficient," *IEEE Trans. Parallel Distrib. Syst.*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 1073–1080, 2012
- [9] T. Peng, "Detecting Reflector Attacks by Sharing Beliefs" Proceedings of GLOBECOM'03, pp. 1358-1362 (2003)
- [10] V. Paxson, "An analysis of using reflectors for distributed denial-of-service attacks," *ACM Computer Communication. Rev.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 38–47, 2001.
- [11] Robin R. (2016) "Encryption scheme with unlimited Key Size and Dynamic Functionality", MASK International Journal of Science and Technology, Vol. 1 no. 1, pp-8-11.